

The Effect of the Quantum $\exp(ipx)$ in a Potential on a Particle's Probabilities

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It is known that a single photon moving in the x direction and encountering an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction discontinuity at x_0 will either reflect or refract, with the probabilities for each summing to 1. This problem, however, is solved using a balance of $A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx) = C\exp(ip_2 x)$ at x_0 and the derivative d/dx , of this equation. The complex conjugate of one equation multiplied by the second yields: $AA/c = BB/c + CC/c^2$ where $E=pc$ and E is constant for the incident, reflected and refracted photon. The two continuity equations apply even in the case of a single photon, but in such a case one has either an incident photon changing to a reflected one or an incident to a refracted one. One never has all three together as in the two continuity equations. We ask: How is it possible to include both a refracted and reflected photon together with the incident in the same equation?

We suggest here that the form $\exp(ipx)$ applies to momentum, whether it is part of a particle or part of a potential field. $\exp(ipx)$ may be obtained from maximization of entropy $-P(x)\ln(P(x))$ subject to the periodic constraint $ipxP(x)$. We suggest that in a single photon interaction, one has momentum in media n_1 and n_2 and these allow for the continuity equation with the system interactions taking the place of a photon to create the balance. There is stochasticity in that a single photon either becomes a reflected or refracted one, but $\exp(ipx)$ does not simply apply to the photon. It may be applied to the n_1 - n_2 interface momentum which is created during the interaction. This interaction is consistent with the a steady stream picture only involving photons. Thus for a single photon, it appears as if one has an entangled probability $\exp(ipx)$'s for the incident, reflected and refracted photons, but actually the physical photon only plays a role as first an incident one and then either a reflected or refracted one with the n_1 - n_2 interface momentum creating the missing $\exp(ipx)$ piece needed for the continuity balance. Ultimately, A, B and C become probabilities $AA/c = 1$, $BB/c = P(\text{reflected})$ and $CC/c^2 = P(\text{refracted})$, but these are not obtained by maximizing entropy subject to a constraint as one does not have independence of probabilities. We note that the two continuity equations combine to create a pressure balance which one wishes to have physically in the problem.

The photon reflection-refraction problem may be reformulated for a particle with rest mass using a particle with E, p in a constant potential V_1 reaching a V_1 - V_2 (both constant) interface at x_0 with E remaining constant.

Single Photon Reflection-Refraction

A single photon moving in the x direction may either reflect or refract at an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction interface at x_0 , but not both. As a result, it appears that the stochasticity occurs only in the interaction as in tossing a coin or a die. The problem is that a balance of probability equation:

$1 = P(\text{reflected}) + P(\text{refracted})$ ((1a)) written in terms of flux $AA/c = BB/c + CC/c^2$ with $E=pc$ and

E constant for the incident, reflected and refracted photon, yields a pressure balance equation if one multiplies by E and converts E/c to pi. As a result, instead of two independent equations, one has a single one and cannot solve for B and C in terms of A. Note: AA is written in this manner to indicate it is a positive quantity.

How does one resolve this dilemma? We argue that one should investigate the nature of the interaction more closely. The above analysis completely ignores the wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ of the photon, yet interference-diffraction experiments show that this exists. How does $\exp(ipx)$ have anything to do with the interaction which converts an incident photon into a reflected or refracted one?

$\exp(ipx)$ in terms of Maximization of Entropy

We have suggested in previous notes that one may obtain $\exp(ipx)$ by:

Maximizing $-P(x) \ln(P(x))$ subject to the periodic constraint $i p x P(x)$ ((2))

The point we wish to make here is that p represents momentum in space x and does not necessarily apply only to a particle or photon with momentum. A potential may also manifest the presence of momentum through $\exp(ipx)$. For example, one may write: $V(x)$ in a bound state quantum problem as: $\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$.

We suggest that not only does a particle with momentum p behave according to $\exp(ipx)$, but momenta generated in an interaction between a particle and a potential may behave in the same manner.

If one considers a photon with momentum p which reflects and has - p, but the same energy, the system has rendered an impulse and changed the momentum of the particle. By the idea of action-reaction, the system should encounter a momentum hit as well. This should be manifested by an $\exp(ipx)$ form. We suggest that even if one has a single photon, one wishes to create a balance equation using $\exp(ipx)$ s even though the photon cannot be both a reflected one or a refracted one. If it is one, the system momentum can "create" the other to provide the balance. Thus:

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip^2 x) \text{ at } x_0 \text{ ((3a)) and}$$

$$A \exp(ipx) - p B \exp(-ipx) = C p^2 \exp(ip^2 x) \text{ at } x_0 \text{ ((3b))}$$

represent photon-system momentum balance equations, because any momentum, photon or system, may be manifested in an $\exp(ipx)$ form and there must be an overall balance.

Taking the complex conjugate of ((3a)) and multiplying by ((3b)) yields a pressure balance at x_0 if AA is considered to be flux. This pressure balance must exist on physical grounds, but is created by the system and photon momenta behaving according to $\exp(ipx)$. Furthermore, this pressure balance equation is identical to a probability balance because $p=E/c$ and E is the same for the incident, reflected and refracted photons. Thus AA/c is the number of incident

photons, BB/c the reflected and CC/c^2 the refracted. If AA/c is set to 1, the other two numbers become probabilities.

In other words, probabilities AA/c , BB/c and CC/c^2 are not created a priori as in the case of a coin or die, but emerge from balance equations ((3a)) and ((3b)) in which they do not even appear as probabilities. It is only through the combination of the two continuity equations that the notion of a reflected or refracted probability emerges.

The balance equations ((3a)) and ((3b)) give the appearance of entangled photon probabilities, i.e. the incident, reflected and refracted $\exp(ipx)$ s interacting with each other, but we suggest it may be momentum stirred up in the system during the interaction which accounts for the balance equation as a single photon may become either a reflected or refracted one, but not both.

In the case of a particle with rest mass, one may have E and p in a region of constant V_1 hitting a V_1 - V_2 interface at x_0 (V_2 constant as well), with E remaining constant. We argue that the same ideas as above apply.

Speculation on Two-Slit Interference

We suggest that there are some similarities between the reflection/refraction problem and two-slit interference. In both cases, a photon is physically associated with one route, i.e. reflection or refraction or passing through one slit or the other. The calculation for each problem, however, considers both routes and allows for interference. We argued that in the reflection-refraction scenario, if a photon reflects and is represented by $B\exp(-ipx)$ (LHS), then the system momentum is associated with $C\exp(ip2x)$ (RHS) and vice versa. Thus it appears as if one considers $B\exp(-ipx)$ and $C\exp(ip2x)$ for both a reflected and refracted photon at the same time. The system plays one of the roles so one cannot determine whether the photon is the reflected or refracted one until after the interaction.

We speculate that a similar thing may happen with two slit interference. The photon has a wavelength \hbar/p and may interact with both slits. One has no idea through which slit it passes but it only passes through one. If it passes through the first, it is represented by $\exp(ip \cdot x')$ where x' is a vector from the slit system to the screen. An impulse hit occurs changing the initial photon momentum direction and so there is system momentum. The system may create the $\exp(ip \cdot x')$ with system momentum so that the sum gives the appearance of interference of the photon going through one hole and the other together. This interaction need only take place at the two slit system in order to establish the probability of the photon to move in one direction or another.

Conclusion

In conclusion, probabilities may be manifested due to an interaction. For example, one must toss a coin or die. In a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, one has collisions which redistribute energy. In these situations the particle is in some well-defined state which changes stochastically due to the interaction.

In the case of a photon moving in the x direction and reflecting or refracting at an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction interface at x_0 , there is a condition on the probability behaviour or momentum in x .

In particular, from maximization of $-P(x)\ln(P(x))$ subject to $ipxP(x)$, it follows that an $\exp(ipx)$ form exists. A single photon may either reflect or refract, it cannot do both. The photon retains its energy regardless, but not its momentum. There is a momentum discontinuity which the system must deal with. This system reaction momentum should also be manifested in the $\exp(ipx)$ form, we argue. This implies that the interaction with the photon together with system momentum may create a balance of $\exp(ipx)$ functions and their first derivatives, i.e. one may write ((3a)) and ((3b)).

This at first looks like two equations including both a reflected and refracted photon, but really these are equations of momenta. Nowhere does one explicitly imply that the momentum belongs to a photon. It could belong to the system. The system momentum and the photon momentum create the balance equations, but if the photon is a reflected one, the system behaves as a refracted one and vice versa. The balance equations introduce weights A,B,C for the incident, reflected and refracted photons, but it is not until one takes the complex conjugate of the first balance equation and multiplies it by the second, that one obtains $1 = P(\text{reflected}) + P(\text{refracted})$. As a result, this problem does not follow from an overall maximization of entropy subject to constraints, but rather deals with the $\exp(ipx)$ form (which represents a kind of maximization of entropy for momentum), but applies to both the photon and system momentum.